

1 **Appendices** for ‘Temperature-dependent evolutionary speed shapes the evolution of biodiversity
2 patterns across tetrapod radiations’

3

4 **Authors**

5 Skeels, A. ^{*,1,2}, Bach, W. ^{1,2}, Hagen, O ^{1,2,3}, Jetz, W. ^{4,5}, Pellissier, L. ^{1,2}

6 * Corresponding author. Email: alexander.skeels@usys.ethz.ch / alexander.skeels@gmail.com

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8 **Affiliations**

9 ¹ Department of Environmental Systems Sciences, Landscape Ecology, Institute of Terrestrial
10 Ecosystems, ETH Zürich, Zurich 8092, Switzerland.

11 ² Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL, Birmensdorf 8903,
12 Switzerland

13 ³ German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig, Leipzig 04103,
14 Germany

15 ⁴ Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, Yale University, New Haven, Connecticut
16 06520, USA

17 ⁵ Center for Biodiversity and Global Change, Yale University, New Haven, CT 06520, USA.

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19 **Appendices**

20 **Appendix 1. Supplementary Figures**

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25

26 **Appendix 1. Supplementary Figures**

27

28 **Figure S1.** Empirical distribution of root ages for taxonomic orders of tetrapods based on fossil-
29 calibrated molecular phylogenies. The red line marks 65 Ma, the age of the simulated clades.

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33 **Figure S2.** Temperature, aridity, and species richness sampled at seven time points and standardised
 34 between 0 and 1. Temperature and aridity values are based on climatic and geological reconstructions.
 35 Species richness is shown from one randomly sampled simulation model as an example of how
 36 biodiversity patterns emerge in the model over deep time.

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39 **Figure S3.** Density distribution of 1000 random samples draw from Weibull distributions with scale
40 parameter (Ψ) equal to 2.5 and shape parameter (Φ) equal to 440 (grey), 660 (yellow), or 880 (blue).

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 44 the environment (T_j) and the population's temperature optimum (T_i). Smaller values of ω lead to
 45 stricter environmental filtering, and species that are poorly adapted to the site have lower abundances.

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48 **Figure S5.** Maximum carrying capacity (K) for individuals across all species within each site as a
49 function of the aridity index [11036, 30000].

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52

53 **Figure S6.** Stochastic probability of extirpation of a population within a site as a function of
54 population size (N_{ij}). The probability declines as a step function of population size, with extirpation
55 probability high for smaller populations (<1000) and low for larger populations (>1000).

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57

58 **Figure S7.** Simulated evolution of a neutral trait representing either the temperature optima (T_i) or

59 body size (B_i) under a Brownian motion model of evolution bounded between values of 0 and 1

60 across 390 timesteps. High values of the evolutionary rate parameter, σ (yellow) lead to larger

61 changes in the trait value in shorter periods than under low values of σ (blue).

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64 **Figure S8.** Heatmaps showing the increase in genetic divergence between populations i and k at each
 65 time step (G_{ik}) based on mean values of temperature across each population's geographic range (T) or
 66 mean body size of each population (B), depending on the model of population divergence (M1–M3).

67 When $\lambda = 1$ divergence scales linearly with B or T (a), whereas when $\lambda > 1$ divergence is
 68 exponentially related to B or T (b-c), with divergence accruing slowly between populations occupying
 69 colder regions, and rapidly only in the populations occurring in the warmest sites.

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72 **Figure S9.** Distribution of clade sizes in each data set with boxplots detailing statistical moments.

73 emp65 = empirical data set based on time-slice clades at 65 Ma; empOrder = empirical data set based

74 on taxonomic orders; sim = complete simulated dataset; simLD = simulated dataset subset to include

75 only clades with fewer than 1000 species.

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78 **Figure S10.** Distributions of the mean and range of 53 biodiversity summary statistics between empirical
 79 simulated datasets after scaling and centring values for visual comparison. Overlap between summary statistics
 80 was done prior to scaling. ED = species-specific evolutionary distinctiveness using fair proportion measure
 81 (Isaac et al. 2007; Kembel et al. 2010); DR = species-specific diversification rate tip metric measured as the
 82 inverse of ED(Jetz et al. 2012); MRD = mean root distance measured using Abouheif's method (MRDa) and the
 83 number of nodes (MRDn), or the sum of direct descendants methods (MRDs)(Jombart et al. 2010); MPD =
 84 mean pairwise distance(Webb 2000; Constantinos and Brody 2015); MNTD = mean nearest taxon
 85 distance(Webb 2000; Kembel et al. 2010); PD = phylogenetic diversity(Kembel et al. 2010; Constantinos and
 86 Brody 2015); lat. = latitude; temp. = temperature. ρ = Spearman correlation coefficient.

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89 **Figure S11.** First two principal components of a Principal component analysis of 26 uncorrelated
 90 summary statistics for simulated and empirical datasets. Separate panels show different separations of
 91 the data. Left hand side: separation between empirical data (Taxonomic orders) and four different
 92 simulation models (M0-M3). Right hand side: separation between two separate empirical data sets
 93 and the combined simulated data. Ellipses envelop 95% of points in each category.

94

95 **Figure S12.** Global sensitivity analysis of biodiversity summary statistics to model parameters: the strength of
 96 environmental filtering for the temperature niche trait (ω), the rate of body-size evolution under Brownian
 97 motion (σ_B), the rate of temperature niche evolution (σ_T), the dispersal kernel (Φ), the rate scaling factor for the
 98 rate of population divergence under M1–M3 (λ), the divergence threshold (S), and the model of population
 99 divergence (M). (a) Pseudo-R² representing the variance in each summary statistic that can be explained by the
 100 simulation model parameters estimated using Boosted Regression Trees (BRT). (b) The contribution of each
 101 parameter to the BRT. ED = species-specific evolutionary distinctiveness using fair proportion measure (Isaac et
 102 al. 2007; Kembel et al. 2010); DR = species-specific diversification rate tip metric measured as the inverse of
 103 ED (Jetz et al. 2012); MRD = mean root distance measured using Abouheif's method (MRDa), the number of
 104 nodes (MRDn), or the sum of direct descendants methods (MRDs) (Jombart et al. 2010); MPD = mean pairwise

105 distance (Webb 2000; Constantinos and Brody 2015); MNTD = mean nearest taxon distance (Webb 2000;
106 Kembel et al. 2010); PD = phylogenetic diversity (Kembel et al. 2010; Constantinos and Brody 2015); lat. =
107 latitude; temp. = temperature. ρ = Spearman correlation coefficient.

108

109 **Figure S13.** Variance in the validation metric (pseudo-R²) estimated using boosted regression trees
 110 with increasing simulation size. (a) Line plot which follows the change in pseudo-R² for each
 111 summary statistic. (b) The same information, but instead showing the distribution of all pseudo-R²
 112 values for each sample size.

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115 **Figure S14.** Stability in the estimated variable contribution to boosted regression trees with increasing
 116 sample size. Values approaching 1 represent more stable estimates of the parameter contribution (i.e.
 117 lower values represent greater stability). The top panel is a line plot which follows the change in
 118 stability for each summary statistic. The bottom panel shows the same information, but instead shows
 119 the distribution of all stability values for each sample size. Both plots highlight that stability
 120 approaches a value of 1 with increasing sample size.

121

122 **Figure S15.** First two principal components of a Principal component analysis of 26 uncorrelated
 123 summary statistics for simulated dataset, each point is coloured by one of six model parameters: the
 124 strength of environmental filtering for the temperature niche trait (ω), the rate of body-size evolution under
 125 Brownian motion (σ_B), the rate of temperature niche evolution (σ_T), the dispersal kernel (Φ), the rate scaling
 126 factor for the rate of population divergence under M1–M3 (λ), and the divergence threshold (S).

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130 **Figure S16.** Inter-correlations between 53 summary statistics. ED = species-specific evolutionary
 131 distinctiveness using fair proportion measure (Isaac et al. 2007; Kembel et al. 2010); DR = species-
 132 specific diversification rate tip metric measured as the inverse of ED(Jetz et al. 2012); MRD = mean
 133 root distance measured using Abouheif’s method (MRDa), the number of nodes (MRDn), or the sum
 134 of direct descendants methods (MRDs) (Jombart et al. 2010); MPD = mean pairwise distance(Webb
 135 2000; Constantinou and Brody 2015); MNTD = mean nearest taxon distance(Webb 2000; Kembel et

136 al. 2010); PD = phylogenetic diversity(Kembel et al. 2010; Constantinos and Brody 2015); lat. =
137 latitude; temp. = temperature. ρ = Spearman correlation coefficient.

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140 **Figure S17.** Mean and 95% confidence intervals of two metrics of model reclassification accuracy,
 141 (a) absolute accuracy and (b) Cohen's κ , using seven machine learning algorithms from cross
 142 validation using a two-thirds training dataset. Machine learning algorithms(Kuhn 2016): GBM =
 143 gradient-boosting model, RF = random forest, LDA = linear discriminant analysis, SVM = support
 144 vector machine, rpart = recursive partitioning and regression trees, NBayes = naïve Bayes, NeuralNet
 145 = neural networks using model averaging.

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148 **Figure S18.** Sum of population-divergence model (M) of best fit across clades for seven different
 149 machine learning algorithms. Each clade contributes seven values to the tally based on the seven
 150 different algorithms. Panels A-B sum to 1148 (164 time-slice clades) panels C-F sum to 336 (48
 151 taxonomic orders). Each row represents a different dataset of empirical summary statistics, the top
 152 row (A-B) is based on time-sliced clades, the middle row (C-D) is based on taxonomic orders with
 153 phylogenetic metrics estimated on the maximum clade credibility tree (MCC), and the bottom row (E-
 154 F) is based on taxonomic orders and phylogenetic metrics taken as the mean value across 50 trees
 155 sampled from the posterior distribution of the clade. Each column represents a different subset of
 156 simulations used to train the machine learning algorithms (All sims = all simulations; LD = low
 157 diversity simulations).

158

159 **Figure S19.** Relationship between spearman correlations of species richness and temperature at two
160 spatial scales: 220km x 200km grid cells and bioregions.

161 **Appendix 2. Supplementary Tables**

162 **Table S1.** Name, class, and definitions of 54 summary statistics investigated in this study. Many
 163 statistics are based on correlations between traits measured at the species level or are correlations
 164 between community-level property values estimated at the site level (220 km × 220 km grid cells
 165 across the globe). Statistic classes are: 1 = phylogenetic metric correlations, 2 = trait metric
 166 correlations and distributions, 3 = phylogenetic tree size and shape, and 4 = spatial metric
 167 correlations. ES = species-specific evolutionary distinctiveness using the equal splits measure
 168 (Redding and Mooers 2006; Kembel et al. 2010); ED = species-specific evolutionary distinctiveness
 169 using the fair proportion measure (Isaac et al. 2007; Kembel et al. 2010); DR = species-specific
 170 diversification rate tip metric measured as the inverse of ES (Jetz et al. 2012); MRD = mean root
 171 distance measured using Abouheif’s method (MRDa), the number of nodes (MRDn), or the sum of
 172 direct descendant methods (MRDs) (Jombart et al. 2010); MPD = mean pairwise distance (Webb
 173 2000; Constantinos and Brody 2015); MNTD = mean nearest taxon distance (Webb 2000; Kembel et
 174 al. 2010); PD = phylogenetic diversity (Kembel et al. 2010; Constantinos and Brody 2015); lat. =
 175 latitude; temp. = temperature; ρ = Spearman correlation coefficient.

Summary statistic	Statistic class	Definition
body size ~ DR ρ	1	Spearman’s correlation coefficient (ρ) of body size and the diversification rate tip metric statistic
body size ~ ED ρ	1	ρ of body size and evolutionary distinctiveness using the fair proportions approach
body size ~ ES ρ	1	ρ of body size and evolutionary distinctiveness using the equal splits metric
body size ~ MRDa ρ	1	ρ of body size and mean root distance computed using Abouheif distances
body size ~ MRDn ρ	1	ρ of body size and mean root distance computed using the number of nodes separating taxa from the root
body size ~ MRDs ρ	1	ρ of body size mean root distance computed using the sum of direct descendants
body size ~ range size ρ	2	ρ of body size and geographic range size

body size ~ temp. ρ	2	ρ of body size and temperature niche position
body size ~ kurtosis	2	kurtosis of body size distribution
body size ~ skewness	2	skewness of body size distribution
clade size	3	Number of species in the clade
Colless' I	3	Sackin's index of phylogenetic tree imbalance
γ	3	gamma statistic for phylogenetic node height distribution
lat. ~ body size mean ρ	4	ρ of absolute latitude and mean body size
lat. ~ body size SD ρ	4	ρ of absolute latitude and the standard deviation of body size
lat. ~ MNTD ρ	4	ρ of absolute latitude and mean nearest taxon phylogenetic distance standardised for species richness
lat. ~ MPD ρ	4	ρ of absolute latitude and mean pairwise phylogenetic distance standardised for species richness
Lat. ~ PD ρ	4	ρ of absolute latitude and phylogenetic diversity standardised for species richness
MNTD ~ body size mean ρ	4	ρ of mean nearest taxon phylogenetic distance standardised for species richness and mean body size
MNTD ~ body size SD ρ	4	ρ of mean nearest taxon phylogenetic distance standardised for species richness and the standard deviation of body size
MPD ~ body size mean ρ	4	ρ of mean pairwise phylogenetic distance standardised for species richness and mean body size
MPD ~ body size SD ρ	4	ρ of mean pairwise phylogenetic distance standardised for species richness and the standard deviation of body size
PD ~ body size mean ρ	4	ρ of phylogenetic diversity standardised for species richness and mean body size
PD ~ body size SD ρ	4	ρ of phylogenetic diversity standardised for species richness and the standard deviation of body size
range size ~ DR ρ	1	ρ of range size and the diversification rate tip metric statistic
range size ~ ED ρ	1	ρ of range size and evolutionary distinctiveness
range size ~ ES ρ	1	ρ of range size and the equal splits metric
range size ~ MRDa ρ	1	ρ of range size and mean root distance computed using Abouheif distances
range size ~ MRDn ρ	1	ρ of range size and mean root distance computed using the number of nodes separating taxa from the root

range size ~ MRDs ρ	1	ρ of mean root distance computed using the sum of direct descendants
range size ~ temp ρ	2	ρ of geographic range size and temperature niche position
richness ~ body size mean ρ	4	ρ of species richness and mean body size
richness ~ body size SD ρ	4	ρ of species richness and the standard deviation of body size
richness ~ lat. ρ	4	ρ of species richness and absolute latitude
richness ~ MNTD ρ	4	ρ of species richness and mean nearest taxon phylogenetic distance standardised for species richness
richness ~ MPD ρ	4	ρ of species richness and mean pairwise phylogenetic distance standardised for species richness
richness ~ PD ρ	4	ρ of species richness and phylogenetic diversity standardised for species richness
richness ~ temp ρ	4	ρ of species richness and temperature
range size kurtosis	2	kurtosis of range size distribution
range size skewness	2	skewness of range size distribution
Sackin's Index	3	Sackin's index of phylogenetic tree imbalance
temp. ~ body size mean ρ	4	ρ of temperature and mean body size
temp. ~ body size SD ρ	4	ρ of temperature and the standard deviation of body size
temp. ~ DR ρ	1	ρ of temperature niche position and the diversification rate tip metric statistic
temp. ~ ED ρ	1	ρ of temperature niche position and evolutionary distinctiveness
temp. ~ ES ρ	1	ρ of temperature niche position and the equal splits metric
temp. kurtosis	2	kurtosis of temperature niche position distribution
temp. ~ MNTD ρ	4	ρ of temperature and mean nearest taxon phylogenetic distance standardised for species richness
temp. ~ MPD ρ	4	ρ of temperature and mean pairwise phylogenetic distance standardised for species richness
temp. ~ MRDa ρ	1	ρ of temperature niche position and mean root distance computed using Abouheif distances
temp. ~ MRDn ρ	1	ρ of temperature niche position and mean root distance computed using the number of nodes separating taxa from the root

temp. ~ MRDs ρ	1	ρ of temperature niche position and mean root distance computed using the sum of direct descendants
temp. ~ PD ρ	4	ρ of temperature and phylogenetic diversity standardised for species richness
temp. skewness	2	skewness of temperature niche position distribution

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178 **Table S2.** Model classification statistics derived from confusion matrix for seven machine learning
179 (ML) algorithms. GBM = gradient-boosting model, RF = random forest, LDA = linear discriminant
180 analysis, SVM = support vector machine, rpart = recursive partitioning and regression trees, NBayes
181 = naïve Bayes, NeuralNet = neural networks using model averaging.

Algorithm	Model	Sensitivity	Specificity	Precision	Detection rate	Balanced Accuracy
LDA	M0	0.795	0.913	0.756	0.202	0.854
LDA	M1	0.795	0.926	0.774	0.193	0.86
LDA	M2	0.716	0.904	0.716	0.18	0.81
LDA	M3	0.603	0.893	0.654	0.152	0.748
RF	M0	0.795	0.933	0.802	0.202	0.864
RF	M1	0.821	0.914	0.754	0.2	0.868
RF	M2	0.776	0.913	0.75	0.195	0.844
RF	M3	0.638	0.916	0.718	0.161	0.777
rpart	M0	0.821	0.895	0.727	0.208	0.858
rpart	M1	0.723	0.94	0.794	0.176	0.832
rpart	M2	0.681	0.87	0.637	0.171	0.775
rpart	M3	0.534	0.881	0.602	0.134	0.708
NeuralNet	M0	0.769	0.924	0.776	0.195	0.847
NeuralNet	M1	0.777	0.92	0.757	0.189	0.848
NeuralNet	M2	0.784	0.91	0.746	0.197	0.847
NeuralNet	M3	0.681	0.916	0.731	0.171	0.798
GBM	M0	0.761	0.922	0.767	0.193	0.841
GBM	M1	0.83	0.92	0.769	0.202	0.875
GBM	M2	0.767	0.948	0.832	0.193	0.858
GBM	M3	0.767	0.919	0.761	0.193	0.843
SVM	M0	0.821	0.933	0.807	0.208	0.877
SVM	M1	0.821	0.911	0.748	0.2	0.866
SVM	M2	0.793	0.901	0.73	0.2	0.847
SVM	M3	0.586	0.928	0.731	0.148	0.757

NBayes	M0	0.641	0.878	0.641	0.163	0.759
NBayes	M1	0.705	0.842	0.59	0.171	0.774
NBayes	M2	0.707	0.91	0.726	0.178	0.809
NBayes	M3	0.569	0.91	0.68	0.143	0.74

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184 **Table S3.** Mean proportion of clades with the best fitting model across seven machine learning
 185 algorithms based on six different model selection procedures or datasets. LD = low diversity
 186 simulation training dataset. MCC = phylogenetic metrics from maximum clade credibility phylogeny.
 187 Posterior = phylogenetic metrics taken as mean cross 50 trees from posterior distribution of
 188 phylogenetic analysis. Main analysis refers to the analysis presented in the main text.

Analysis	Figure S19 panel	M0	M1	M2	M3
Time-slice clades	A	0.173	0.647	0.047	0.132
Time-slice clades (LD)	B	0.042	0.760	0.041	0.158
Taxonomic order (MCC)	C	0.202	0.628	0.054	0.116
Taxonomic order (MCC; LD)	D	0.021	0.760	0.057	0.167
Main analysis - Taxonomic order (posterior)	E	0.188	0.562	0.101	0.148
Taxonomic order (posterior; LD)	F	0.018	0.723	0.068	0.190

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191 **Table S4.** Population divergence submodels with the best fit from seven different classification
192 algorithms and the kappa-weighted average posterior support for each submodel for clades of
193 tetrapods. GBM = gradient-boosting model, RF = random forest, LDA = linear discriminant analysis,
194 SVM = support vector machine, rpart = recursive partitioning and regression trees, NBayes = naïve
195 Bayes, NeuralNet = neural networks using model averaging.

Clade	LDA	RF	rpart	NeuralNet	GBM	SVM	NBayes	M0	M1	M2	M3
Serpentes	M2	M1	M1	M3	M1	M3	M1	0.137	0.429	0.184	0.250
Anguimorpha	M1	M1	M1	M3	M3	M3	M1	0.072	0.466	0.037	0.424
Gekkota	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	0.113	0.866	0.004	0.017
Iguania	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0	M3	M1	0.428	0.277	0.062	0.233
Lacertoidea	M1	M1	M1	M0	M1	M1	M1	0.2	0.781	0.004	0.016
Scincoidea	M3	M3	M3	M3	M3	M3	M3	0.013	0.079	0.13	0.778
Serpentes	M2	M1	M1	M3	M1	M3	M1	0.073	0.486	0.129	0.311
Afrosoricida	M1	M0	M1	M2	M0	M2	M2	0.201	0.376	0.326	0.097
Carnivora	M1	M1	M1	M3	M1	M1	M3	0.071	0.562	0.068	0.298
Cetartiodactyla	M3	M1	M1	M1	M1	M3	M1	0.051	0.443	0.184	0.322
Chiroptera	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	0.114	0.846	0.004	0.036
Cingulata	M3	M0	M1	M3	M0	M3	M1	0.223	0.295	0.115	0.366
Dasyuromorphia	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	0.163	0.819	0.004	0.014
Cidelphimorphia	M1	M0	M0	M1	M2	M1	M1	0.366	0.428	0.129	0.078
Ciprotodontia	M1	M1	M1	M1	M0	M1	M1	0.151	0.763	0.024	0.061
Eulipotyphla	M3	M3	M3	M3	M2	M3	M2	0.025	0.078	0.349	0.548
Lagomorpha	M3	M1	M1	M1	M3	M3	M1	0.074	0.541	0.041	0.344
Primates	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0	M3	M1	0.489	0.276	0.047	0.188
Rodentia	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	0.079	0.877	0.004	0.04
Accipitriformes	M1	M1	M1	M1	M2	M1	M1	0.086	0.603	0.132	0.179
Anseriformes	M0	M0	M0	M0	M1	M1	M0	0.462	0.468	0.018	0.052
Apodiformes	M2	M3	M3	M2	M2	M2	M1	0.008	0.143	0.624	0.225
Bucerotiformes	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	0.052	0.934	0.004	0.01
Caprimulgiformes	M3	M2	M3	M2	M2	M2	M1	0.014	0.124	0.406	0.457
Charadriiformes	M1	M1	M1	M0	M0	M1	M0	0.423	0.55	0.009	0.019
Columbiformes	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	0.113	0.862	0.004	0.021
Coraciiformes	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	0.063	0.769	0.023	0.144
Cuculiformes	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	0.063	0.902	0.002	0.033
Falconiformes	M1	M1	M0	M1	M1	M1	M1	0.205	0.753	0.01	0.031
Galliformes	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	0.246	0.727	0.007	0.021
Gruiformes	M1	M1	M0	M1	M1	M1	M1	0.169	0.794	0.008	0.029
Musophagiformes	M1	M0	M0	M3	M1	M3	M0	0.277	0.345	0.083	0.294
Otidiformes	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M1	M0	0.327	0.579	0.033	0.06
Passeriformes	M2	M1	M1	M3	M1	M3	M1	0.089	0.396	0.167	0.349

Pelecaniformes	M3	M3	M3	M3	M2	M0	M3	0.192	0.152	0.19	0.465
Piciformes	M0	M1	M1	M0	M0	M0	M1	0.481	0.49	0.01	0.019
Procellariiformes	M1	0.089	0.894	0.002	0.016						
Psittaciformes	M3	M3	M3	M3	M2	M3	M1	0.042	0.276	0.13	0.552
Strigiformes	M3	M1	M1	M3	M3	M3	M1	0.056	0.463	0.082	0.399
Suliformes	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0	M0	M1	0.668	0.289	0.021	0.022
Tinamiformes	M2	M3	M2	M2	M1	M2	M1	0.046	0.255	0.552	0.147
Trogoniformes	M1	M1	M1	M0	M1	M1	M1	0.154	0.824	0.003	0.019
Anura	M2	M1	M1	M3	M1	M3	M3	0.08	0.3	0.244	0.376
Caudata	M1	M3	M3	M3	M1	M3	M3	0.022	0.433	0.124	0.422
Gymnophiona	M1	0.105	0.863	0.009	0.023						
Crocodylia	M1	M1	M1	M0	M1	M1	M1	0.189	0.791	0.003	0.017
Testudines	M1	0.199	0.674	0.015	0.112						

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198 **Appendix 3. Extended methods**

199 1. Data generation and collation

200 *1.1 Simulation model*

201 *1.1.1 Overview*

202 We implemented a spatial model of diversification using the general engine for eco-evolutionary
203 simulations, *gen3sis* (Hagen et al. 2021a). The *gen3sis* software provides a modular simulation engine
204 that follows population- and species-level dynamics across a gridded landscape. *Gen3sis* allows users
205 to specify custom functions for four core processes in the model: dispersal, trait evolution, speciation,
206 and ecological interactions / community assembly. These processes interact with a gridded landscape,
207 moving forward through time at discrete time steps. Biodiversity patterns emerge through the
208 interaction of these processes and how together they shape macroevolutionary dynamics of speciation,
209 extinction, and dispersal. Each simulation provides: (i) a phylogenetic chronogram showing the
210 relationships of species and the timing of speciation and extinction events; (ii) the spatial distribution
211 of each population for each species on the gridded global landscape; and (iii) the traits of each
212 population for each species. These features allow us to summarise simulated biodiversity patterns in
213 several ways typical for biodiversity studies (see 1.2 for details).

214 In this study, each simulation follows the diversification of a clade from a single ancestral species at
215 the beginning of the Cenozoic (65 Ma). As a simplifying assumption, we had the ancestral lineage
216 occur in every grid cell at 65 Ma. This removes any artefact of residence time in the emergence of
217 biodiversity patterns and gives the clade a global distribution, matching many clades which originated
218 or diversified during the early Cenozoic period (e.g. mammal and bird orders). We used global
219 reconstructions of temperature and aridity from 65 Ma to the present day at ~170,000-year time steps
220 (390 time steps in total) as input landscapes (Fig. S2). Following Hagen et al. (Hagen et al. 2021b),
221 temperature was reconstructed from paleo estimates of the distribution of climatic Koeppen bands
222 (Scotese et al. 2021), a temperature curve based on oxygen isotope data (Scotese et al.
223 2021) and digital elevation models (Scotese and Wright 2018). The aridity index was taken as the

224 ‘subtropical arid’ Koeppen band, and therefore is a boundary layer representing the approximate
225 location of arid and humid sites. The paleo-reconstructions were transformed from 1 degree latitude
226 and longitude resolution to a resolution of 220 km × 220 km equal-area grid cells, using the
227 Behrmann transformation. The temperature and aridity values were also scaled to be between 0 and 1,
228 representing the minimum and maximum values across all time steps.

229 Each species in the simulation has four traits: dispersal (D), temperature niche optimum (T),
230 temperature niche width (T_w), and body size (B). D and T_w are fixed across all species within a
231 simulation but vary between simulations (see below for parameter exploration), while T and B evolve
232 independently and therefore vary between species within a simulation. Values of both T and B vary
233 between 0 and 1. T values directly match the scaled temperature values of the environment and
234 represent an optimal temperature value of the species niche (see below for details). However, the unit
235 of body size is arbitrary and intentionally unit-free in order to match body-size data in various formats
236 (for example, snout-vent-length in reptiles or body mass in mammals) and ranges in the empirical
237 data. Because the unit of body size is arbitrary, this trait could also theoretically represent life history
238 traits directly – e.g. generation time – but we selected body size because it is the most widely
239 available trait in real data for comparison.

240

241 We will now go through each custom function for the four core processes implemented in *gen3sis*.

242 *1.1.2 Dispersal*

243 At each time step, each population of each species can colonise surrounding grid cells from their
244 present location. The maximum distance of each dispersal event is drawn from a dispersal kernel with
245 a Weibull distribution, and all connected grid cells within the distance are successfully colonised. If
246 multiple populations of the same species successfully colonise the same grid cell, then one is selected
247 at random. The new population takes the traits of the successful colonist. A Weibull distribution with
248 a fixed shape parameter ($\Psi = 2.5$) was used, and the scale parameter (Φ) was sampled between 330
249 and 880 (Fig. S3).

250

251 *1.1.3 Ecological interactions / Community assembly*

252 Each grid cell (site) on the landscape acts as an ecological community, with the presence, absence,
253 and abundance of each population determined by a set of ecological rules. In this study, sites have
254 fixed ecological carrying capacities for the absolute number of all individuals across species.

255 Population size N_{ij} of each population i in site j is determined by a Gaussian function of resource use
256 efficiency – the distance between the environmental value in each grid cell (T_j) and the population's
257 environmental niche trait (T_i) – following (McPeck 2007; McPeck 2008) (Fig. S4):

258
$$N_{ij} = K * \exp(-(T_i - T_j/\omega)^2) \quad \text{equation 1}$$

259 where ω is a parameter that determines the niche width (T_w) of all species and controls the strength of
260 environmental filtering, with small values leading to a sharper decline in abundance as the species
261 temperature niche optimum (T_i) becomes more different from the temperature of the site (T_j). N_{ij}
262 equals K in the absence of competitors if species i is perfectly adapted to that environment (T_j).

263 The carrying capacity (K) and each site (j) is spatially heterogeneous and determined based on the
264 aridity (but not temperature) values of each site (A_j), with more arid sites having lower carrying
265 capacities (Fig. S5).

266
$$K = K_c * \exp(-1 * A_j) \quad \text{equation 2}$$

267 Where K_c is a constant and was fixed across simulations at 30,000. Spatially heterogeneous carrying
268 capacities were determined based on empirical evidence that suggests that aridity places a major
269 constraint on abundance and based on previous studies using *gen3sis* which have demonstrated that
270 imposing fixed constraints on aridity (Hagen et al. 2021b) or carrying capacities that are based on
271 aridity (Hagen et al. 2021a) provide a consistently good fit to real biodiversity data. However, this
272 study differs from (Hagen et al. 2021a) in that we do not also base the carrying capacity on
273 temperature. This is because we were interested in the effect of temperature on diversification and did
274 not want to conflate these factors.

275

276 We model a zero-sum game where sites have finite resources available, which places ecological limits
277 on the maximum number of individuals in a site across populations of all species present (N_j).

278 Therefore, if the total community abundance across all species (N_j) is $\geq K$, the addition of any new
279 species decreases the resources available to all present species. In saturated communities ($N_j \geq K$), the
280 realised abundance of each species (\hat{N}_{ij}) is apportioned according to the resource use efficiency of
281 each species, following (Hurlbert and Stegen 2014):

$$282 \quad \hat{N}_{ij} = N_{ij} * \min(N_j, K)/N_j \quad \text{equation 3}$$

283 Local extinction occurs deterministically if $\hat{N}_{ij} = 0$ or stochastically as a sigmoidal function of \hat{N}_{ij} (Fig.
284 S6):

$$285 \quad 1/(1+\exp(-\mu_d * (\mu_t - \hat{N}_{ij}))) \quad \text{equation 4}$$

286 where μ_t is the population size threshold below which extirpation in site j becomes increasingly
287 probable and μ_d is the rate of decay of the function. μ_t was fixed at 1000 and μ_d at 0.1, which led to
288 low probabilities of extinction in larger populations (>1000) and a rapid increase in extinction
289 probability in small populations. Extinction of a species occurs when it no longer occupies any sites.

290

291 *1.1.4 Trait evolution*

292 Evolution of the temperature niche trait (T_i) and body mass (B_i) for each independently evolving
293 population approximates a bounded Brownian motion model of trait evolution. The value of the trait
294 at increasing time intervals of δt is equal to the value of the trait at time t plus a value drawn from a
295 normal distribution with a mean of 0 and standard deviation of σ . Low values of σ require longer
296 periods on average for greater trait divergence to occur, whereas higher values mean that large
297 changes in traits can occur in shorter periods (Fig. S7). The traits themselves are bounded between 0
298 and 1. This is because the temperature values of the environment are standardised between 0 and 1,
299 and the temperature niche trait maps directly onto this environmental space. The absolute values of

300 body size are arbitrary in the simulation and therefore we selected to model the range of this trait to be
301 directly comparable to the temperature niche trait. We modelled rates of temperature niche evolution
302 (σ_T) and rates of body-size evolution (σ_B) separately.

303

304

305 *1.1.5 Population divergence and speciation*

306 Speciation in the *gen3sis* simulation framework is based on an allopatric model of speciation.
307 Populations of a species that become geographically isolated from each other diverge at each time
308 step. Divergence is measured as pairwise distances between allopatric populations of a species and
309 can be interpreted as genetic divergence, ecological divergence, or both. In this study, we consider
310 divergence genetic, but it could equally be considered ecological divergence under the evolutionary
311 speed hypothesis.

312 The evolutionary speed hypothesis explicitly makes predictions about rates of population divergence.
313 Therefore, to investigate this hypothesis, we implement four variations of the population divergence
314 function of *gen3sis*. Under the null model (M0), population divergence is independent of temperature
315 or body size. The amount of genetic divergence between populations i and k ($g_{i,k}$) at each time step is
316 drawn from a uniform distribution between 0.01 and 1. Diverging populations become distinct species
317 once genetic divergence has crossed threshold S . We model the effect of migration on genetic
318 differentiation as, if populations have secondary contact (i.e., they return to within-dispersal distance
319 of one another), they coalesce towards genetic homogeneity at a rate of 1 per time step.

320 We additionally model three alternative scenarios in which rates of population divergence are
321 temperature dependent (M1), body-size dependent (M2), or temperature and body-size dependent
322 (M3). Under M1, the genetic divergence of populations i and k ($g_{i,k}$) is a function of the sum of the
323 average temperatures (\hat{T}) experienced by diverging populations i and k across all sites within their
324 geographic range, scaled exponentially with the parameter λ :

325
$$g_{i,k} = ((\hat{T}_i + \hat{T}_k)/2)^\lambda$$
 equation 5

326

327 As temperature values are standardised to be between 0 and 1, the maximum value of g at each time
 328 step is equal to 1, and λ determines the rate of exponential decline towards 0 as species inhabit cooler
 329 grid cells (Fig. S8). When $\lambda = 1$, the rate of population divergence declines linearly, and as λ increases
 330 the population divergence becomes more exponential (Fig. S8). Under M2, $g_{i,k}$ is a function of the
 331 sum of the average standardised body sizes (\hat{B}) of diverging populations i and k , scaled exponentially
 332 with the parameter λ . Body size is standardised to be between 0 and 1 to make the function
 333 comparable with the temperature function. However, as greater genetic divergence is expected in
 334 smaller-bodied species, we use $1 - \hat{B}$:

335
$$g_{i,k} = ((1 - \hat{B}_i + 1 - \hat{B}_k)/2)^\lambda$$
 equation 6

336

337 Here, genetic divergence exponentially approaches 1 as body size decreases, at a rate of λ . Finally,
 338 under M3, $g_{i,k}$ is a function of the average of $1 - \hat{B}$ and \hat{T} (hereafter $\hat{B}\hat{T}$), scaled exponentially with the
 339 parameter λ , such that genetic divergence is faster in small-bodied populations in warmer regions and
 340 decreases exponentially as species increase in body size and occupy cooler grid cells.

341
$$g_{i,k} = ((\hat{B}\hat{T}_i + \hat{B}\hat{T}_k)/2)^\lambda$$
 equation 7

342

343 We ran the simulation model 500 times under each of the 4 scenarios, varying 6 key parameters: the
 344 divergence threshold (S , parameter range = [2, 10]), the rate scaling factor for the rate of population
 345 divergence under M1–M3 (λ , [2, 5]), the strength of environmental filtering for the temperature niche
 346 trait (ω , [0.01, 0.035]), the rate of body-size evolution under Brownian motion (σ_B , [0.001, 0.02]), the
 347 rate of temperature niche evolution (σ_T , [0.001, 0.015]), and the dispersal kernel (Φ , [330, 880]). These
 348 parameter ranges were determined via preliminary examination of the simulation model to broadly
 349 cover a range of conditions while consistently generating clades of comparable size to the empirical

350 data (~20-6000 species; Fig S9). The model is computationally intensive, which restricts the number
351 of replicates possible. To accommodate this limitation, we used a quasi-random sampling technique to
352 select parameter combinations that evenly cover the six-dimensional parameter space (approximating
353 a uniform distribution) and assessed the subsequent parameter sensitivity. Parameter sampling was
354 facilitated using Sobol sequences. It has been shown that strategies that sample parameters broadly
355 and evenly across multidimensional parameter space represent an efficient tool for stochastic
356 simulation models (Prowse et al. 2016)

357

358 2. Simulation model validation and sensitivity analysis

359 *2.1 Model validation*

360 Model validity is determined by exploring whether the simulations provide an accurate representation
361 of real systems, such that they can be used to draw inferences about real processes (Levins 1966).
362 Here, to determine model validity we used two approaches. First, we measured the distribution of
363 each individual summary statistic and calculated the percentage of the empirical estimates of each
364 summary statistic that fell within the range of the simulated data, with a threshold of 95%. We found
365 that 34 summary statistics showed complete overlap with the simulated data, and a further 12 had
366 greater than 95% overlap. Seven variables showed less than 95% overlap (Fig. S10). Of these, five
367 still showed considerable overlap (89–94%; latitude and body-size standard deviation correlation,
368 latitude and body-size mean correlation, phylogenetic diversity and body-size variability correlation,
369 mean pairwise phylogenetic distance and body-size variability correlation, mean nearest taxon
370 phylogenetic distance and body-size variability correlations), while two summary statistics, the
371 skewness and kurtosis of the body-size frequency distribution, were not well represented by the
372 simulated data, with 41% and 52% of empirical clades falling within the simulated data, respectively.
373 These summary statistics highlight that body-size distributions of terrestrial vertebrates are more
374 right-skewed than in the simulated clades. This leads to different patterns of body-size distributions

375 within communities, affecting several correlations that include body-size variability. We discarded
376 these 7 variables from downstream analysis, leading to a dataset with 47 summary statistics.

377 After considering the univariate congruence between empirical and simulated data, we next aimed to
378 investigate whether these data are congruent in multidimensional space. To validate the multivariate
379 distribution, we performed a principal component analysis on the remaining 26 uncorrelated summary
380 statistics (Pearson $r < 0.9$), after first centring and scaling all variables. We then projected the
381 empirical data for both the taxonomic orders, as well as the time-slice clades, in PC space to visualise
382 the overlap (Fig S12). The majority of the empirical data falls within the distribution of summary
383 statistics (Fig S12), with a bias towards higher values of PC1. PC1 explains 19% of the variation in
384 the summary statistics and is negatively associated with clade size, as well as positively associated
385 with metrics measuring the correlation between temperature and speciation rate (MRDn, ES). This
386 provides evidence that the multidimensional congruence of datasets is sufficient.

387

388 *2.2. A note on autocorrelation*

389 Spearman correlations based on properties measured at the species-level or grid-cell level may be
390 biased because the observations are non-independent: species-level properties, such as body size or
391 phylogenetic tip metrics, are more likely to be similar between closely related species, while
392 properties of grid cells, such as species richness, are more likely to be similar between sites in close
393 proximity. Models that account for autocorrelation in the structure of the data are commonly used
394 when drawing inferences about statistical relationships between non-independent observations (such
395 as phylogenetic generalised least squares models (GLS)). In this study, it was not computationally
396 feasible to use parameter estimates from GLS models as summary statistics for the simulated data. We
397 instead use Spearman correlations as summary statistics to describe trends in the simulated and
398 empirical data. We acknowledge that estimated correlation coefficients may reflect true trends in the
399 data or trends that arise spuriously from autocorrelation. We do not draw inferences directly from
400 these correlation coefficients or rely on the direct interpretation of these coefficients for our

401 conclusions (except in section 3.1. and here we repeat the analyses using generalised least squares
402 models that explicitly account for spatial or phylogenetic autocorrelation).

403

404 2.3. *Spatial scale*

405 The spatial resolution of the simulated data (220 km × 220 km) was twice as coarse as the empirical
406 data (110 km × 110 km). We repeated model validation and model selection using the empirical data
407 collated at 110 km × 110 km resolution, aggregating the data to the matching resolution of 220 km ×
408 220 km, and re-estimating the spatial summary statistics. Summary statistics were similar for the two
409 resolutions (Pearson's r , range = [0.95, 0.99], mean = 0.99) and resolution did not have a large impact
410 on downstream analysis, with the main results of the model selection procedure (section 4.1 in SI)
411 remaining unchanged. We present the results of the analysis using summary statistics calculated using
412 the 220 km × 220 km resolution, as this enables a more meaningful comparison.

413 As noted above, we derived several summary statistics from patterns that emerge across grid-cells
414 (including species richness and temperature correlations). Grid cells are not completely independent
415 data because species are found in multiple sites (see above). However, grid cells have some properties
416 that are absent at higher levels of spatial aggregation. For example, assemblages at local spatial scales
417 should contain the signal of community assembly processes (Webb et al. 2006). As such, metrics that
418 attempt to estimate features of functional or phylogenetic community structure (such as mean pairwise
419 phylogenetic distance used in this study) may be more informative of certain processes at this scale,
420 rather than at coarser scales (Mittelbach and Schemske 2015). Further, grid cells lack the problem of
421 determining the biogeographic classification scheme used to define broader regions such as
422 ecoregions or biomes (Olson et al. 2001) which are also not yet possible to model through time in a
423 meaningful way. Previous work has shown that larger biogeographic units, such as bioregions are the
424 ideal spatial scale to investigate regional-scale mechanisms, such as diversification of the regional
425 species pool (Jetz and Fine 2012). However, as we directly model how regional level processes drive
426 local scale assembly patterns, and we find that many of these grid-cell-based metrics vary between the

427 different models of diversification (M0-M3), we feel confident that they capture regional level
428 dynamics. As a final validation of the spatial scale used here, we followed (Jetz and Fine 2012) and
429 estimated species richness of all bioregions. We show how correlation coefficients of species richness
430 and mean bioregion temperature are similar to those estimated using grid-cells (Spearman $\rho = 0.78$,
431 $p < 0.0001$; Fig. S19).

432

433 *2.4 Global sensitivity analysis*

434 To evaluate the relative importance of parameter inputs to biodiversity patterns, we analysed the
435 relationship between each of the 47 retained summary statistics and the 6 variable model parameters,
436 as well as the population divergence submodel (M) using boosted regression trees (Elith et al. 2008),
437 following the protocol of (Prowse et al. 2016). From the original 2000 simulations we discarded those
438 that were incomplete because species became completely extinct, the species number passed the
439 maximum threshold, or ≤ 5 species were generated ($n=1618$). Boosted regression tree models were
440 fitted with Gaussian error, a learning rate of 0.01, a bag fraction of 0.75, and a tree depth of 1,
441 therefore including only first-order interactions between variables. When model fit was not possible
442 with a learning rate of 0.01, we heuristically reduced the rate by 0.001 until a successful model fit was
443 recorded.

444 We extracted pseudo- R^2 from the BRT models to determine how much variation in biodiversity
445 summary statistics was due to variation in model parameters. Pseudo- R^2 ranged from 0.15 to 0.71
446 across the 47 summary statistics, with a mean of 0.43 (Fig. S12). We also recorded the relative
447 contribution of each model parameter to variation in the biodiversity summary statistics by ranking
448 variable importance factors from the BRT models (Fig. S12). The population divergence submodel
449 (M) explained the most variation on average in the biodiversity summary statistics (23.8), followed by
450 the divergence threshold for speciation (S ; 18.2), the shape parameter of the dispersal kernel (Φ ; 16.0),
451 the scaling parameter of the divergence function (λ ; 15.0), rate of temperature niche evolution (σ_T ;
452 15.6), the niche width parameter (ω ; 6.8), and the rate of body-size evolution (σ_B ; 4.6). Variables with

453 the highest pseudo- R^2 values included many spatial biodiversity patterns, such as the correlation
454 between latitude and species richness, and phylogenetic metrics including the gamma statistics and
455 Sackin's index of tree imbalance. Some of the variables had low pseudo- R^2 values, including
456 relationships between mean body size and body-size variability within grid cells, and species richness
457 and temperature. Low pseudo- R^2 values mean that either the patterns were not strongly determined by
458 simulation model parameters and instead were highly stochastic, or the relationships between
459 simulation model parameters and summary statistics were not well characterised using the BRT model
460 parameters (e.g. tree depth), given the sample size of the simulated dataset. The relationship between
461 multidimensional biodiversity summary statistic and model parameters is visualised in two-
462 dimensional space based on PCA in Figure S16. Congruent with the univariate sensitivity analysis, it
463 is apparent that some parameters show clustering in PC space. For example, the divergence threshold
464 (S) and dispersal kernel (Φ) show clear gradients while other parameters appear random with respect
465 to PC space (e.g., σ_B).

466

467 The simulation model is computationally intensive and therefore limited to small sample sizes. To
468 investigate the role of simulation sample size on the sensitivity analysis, we repeated the BRT model
469 sensitivity analysis 20 times with randomly sampled subsets of the simulated dataset of increasing
470 size, from 50 samples to the total number of completed simulations (1618). We compared the
471 distribution and stability of model sensitivity scores following (Prowse et al. 2016). Specifically, we
472 investigated how the estimates of pseudo- R^2 and the estimates of the parameter contributions to the
473 model fit changed as we increased the number of samples. We found that the mean pseudo- R^2 was
474 sensitive to the number of simulations run and decreased with increasing sample size (linear
475 regression, slope = -0.002, t-value = -3.28, $P = 0.004$; Fig. S13). However, the stability of the
476 estimates of parameter contributions to the boosted regression tree model fit increased with sample
477 size (linear regression, slope = -0.005, t-value = -6.17, $P < 0.0001$; Fig. S14), with most statistics
478 approaching stable estimates of parameter contribution when the complete simulated dataset was used
479 ($n=1618$). We found a negative relationship between parameter sensitivity stability (lower values are

480 more stable) and the model validation metric (linear regression, slope = -0.04, t-value = -3.39, P =
481 0.001). This means that statistics with little variation explained by the model parameters had the most
482 variable estimates of parameter contributions. Global sensitivity analysis therefore highlights that the
483 relationship between the simulation model parameters and biodiversity patterns are well characterised
484 for many but not all biodiversity summary statistics, suggesting that some patterns are derived from
485 more complex interactions between model parameters and require larger sample sizes to approximate,
486 or that they emerge from highly stochastic behaviour and cannot be well characterised by the model
487 parameters.

488

489 *2.3 Model discrimination*

490 After characterising how biodiversity patterns are generated by the model parameters and checking
491 the validity of the model in capturing realistic biodiversity patterns, we asked whether biodiversity
492 patterns differ between the population divergence submodels. We subset the complete simulation
493 dataset to include only those simulations whose parameters led to complete simulations under all four
494 submodels of population divergence (1392) to maintain equal sample sizes between model classes.
495 Some summary statistics were colinear (Pearson's $r > 0.95$; Fig. S11) so we removed 21 variables,
496 producing a dataset with 26 summary statistics. We used supervised machine learning model
497 classification tools with 10-fold cross-validation repeated 10 times on a two-thirds training subset of
498 the simulated data (n=917). We then estimated reclassification accuracy based on model predictions
499 on the withheld one-third test dataset (n=467). To investigate the sensitivity of the results to different
500 machine learning algorithms, we used the R package *Caret* to repeat this procedure for seven different
501 classification algorithms: linear discriminant analysis, three decision tree algorithms (recursive
502 partitioning and regression trees, random forest, and a gradient-boosting machine algorithm), naïve
503 Bayes, support-vector machines, and neural networks using model averaging. We assessed model
504 reclassification accuracy regularity across different model classes using sensitivity (true positive rate),
505 specificity (true negative rate), balanced accuracy (sensitivity + specificity)/2, precision (The ratio of
506 correct positives to overall predicted positives), and detection rate (ratio of true positives to total

507 number of predictions; Table S2). After investigating the model discrimination ability between
508 classes, we then ranked the different classification algorithms using global accuracy and Cohen's κ
509 metrics (Fig. S17). We investigated which biodiversity summary statistics were most important in
510 separating the models of population divergence by looking at the relative contribution of each
511 summary statistic using variable importance factors (Fig. 2, main text).

512

513 3. Empirical biodiversity trends

514 *3.1 Empirical data meta-analysis*

515 We used meta-analytical tools to test for general patterns in four key summary statistics across taxa:
516 correlation between body size and the DR phylogenetic metric; correlation between the mean
517 temperature across a species range and the DR phylogenetic metric; correlation between latitude and
518 species richness; correlation between temperature and species richness. These four summary statistics
519 are based on Spearman rank-sum correlations between species-level properties (body size,
520 phylogenetic tip metrics, temperature niche) or grid-cell properties (species richness, latitude, and
521 temperature). We transformed these Spearman correlation coefficients to Z-scores and estimated 95%
522 confidence intervals using Fischer transformations in the R package *DescTools* (Signorell 2021). To
523 see if directional trends existed in the correlations, we estimated the size of the average effect for each
524 of correlation separately using random-effects models and restricted maximum-likelihood estimation
525 in the R package *metafor* (Viechtbauer 2010). As discussed above (Section 1.4), species-level and
526 grid-cell level properties represent non-independent observations. Because here we are drawing direct
527 inference about common trends in the empirical data, we repeated the analysis using standardised
528 regression coefficients from generalised least squares (GLS) models that account for either
529 phylogenetic or spatial autocorrelation in the covariance structure. These were estimated using the *gls*
530 function in the R package *nlme* (Pinheiro et al. 2020), with covariance between species varying as
531 expected under a Brownian motion process in the phylogenetic model, and covariance between sites
532 varying under Gaussian function of their geographic distance in the spatial models.

533

534 **Appendix 4. Extended results**

535 4.1. Empirical biodiversity trends

536 Based on the Spearman correlation coefficients, we found that effects were directional, with
537 temperature showing a positive net effect on species richness ($\beta=0.169\pm0.046$, $Z = 3.688$, $P=0.0002$)
538 and latitude showing a negative net effect on species richness ($\beta = -0.230\pm 0.0581$, $Z = -3.951$,
539 $P<0.001$). Trends in the relationship between speciation rates and body size and between speciation
540 rates (DR) and temperature, however, did not show any directional trends among tetrapods
541 (temperature \sim DR, $\beta = -0.009 \pm 0.008$, $Z = -1.089$, $P=0.28$; body size \sim DR, $\beta = 0.0003\pm 0.0003$, $Z =$
542 0.972 , $P=0.331$). These results were also supported when considering the non-independence of
543 observations using phylogenetic or spatial generalised linear models (species richness \sim temperature,
544 $\beta = 0.002\pm0.0001$, $Z = 10.232$, $P < 0.001$; species richness \sim latitude, $\beta = -0.009 \pm 0.001$, $Z = -10.594$,
545 $P < 0.001$; speciation rates \sim body size, $\beta = -0.0032\pm0.003$, $Z = -1.040$, $P = 0.2982$; speciation rates \sim
546 temperature, $\beta = 0 \pm 0$, $Z = 0.508$, $P = 0.6115$). Specifically, based on the GLS results we found 29
547 significant positive relationships between species richness and temperature, compared to 4 significant
548 negative relationships. We found 34 significant negative relationships between species richness and
549 latitude compared with 3 significant positive relationships. We found 8 significant positive
550 relationships between speciation rate and body size and 16 significant negative relationships. We
551 found 10 significant positive relationships between speciation rates and temperature and 12 significant
552 negative relationships.

553

554 *4.2 Model Selection*

555 We repeated the model selection procedure in several different ways to interrogate the robustness of
556 results to potential biases in the simulated and empirical datasets.

557

558 4.2.1 *Clade age*

559 Firstly, to interrogate the role of clade age in influencing the model selection results, we repeated the
560 model selection procedure on all independent clades of 65 million years of age. To do this, we
561 dissected the maximum clade credibility (MCC) phylogenetic tree for each class at 65 Ma and took all
562 subtrees with more than 20 species (here forth referred to as time-slice clades), resulting in 71
563 amphibian clades, 53 reptile clades, 24 bird clades, and 16 mammal clades. We calculated the 54
564 summary statistics on these clades and predicted the most likely model of population divergence using
565 the 7 machine learning algorithms trained on the simulated dataset. We tallied the best-supported
566 model across clades for each method. We found the relative proportions of best supported models for
567 the time slice clades (Fig S19a) was similar to our main analysis (Fig S19E). M1 was the best
568 supported model in 64.7% of clades on average across the seven machine learning models compared
569 to 56.3% in the main analysis (Table S3).

570

571 4.2.2 *Clade size*

572 Furthermore, while the range of clade sizes was similar between simulated and empirical data sets
573 (Fig. S18), the distribution was different, with empirical data being far more right skewed towards
574 smaller sizes (simulated skewness = 0.23, empirical skewness = 4.45; Fig S10). To investigate
575 whether this difference in clade size distributions influenced the results we repeated the model
576 selection procedure by creating a two-thirds training dataset (n=285) based on a subset of simulations
577 that generated fewer than 1000 species (n= 427). We then fit the seven machine learning models and
578 performed 10-fold cross validation on this reduced training data. Finally, we repeated the model
579 selection procedure using these seven machine learning algorithms and recorded the best fitting model
580 for each clade for the time-slice clades (Figure S19b; Table S3) and taxonomic orders (Figure S19d,f;
581 Table S3). Cross-validation showed a reduced discriminatory power of these models compared to
582 those based on the full dataset, likely due to a reduced sample size. The global reclassification
583 accuracy ranged from 0.57 using the Naïve Bayes algorithm to 0.72 using the model-averaged neural

584 net algorithm (NeuralNet) and Cohen's κ ranged from 0.41 with naïve Bayes and 0.6 using
585 NeuralNet. Values of κ between 0.41- 0.60 are considered weak (McHugh 2012) to moderate (Cohen
586 1960) and results should be interpreted cautiously. Despite, the weaker discriminatory power, overall
587 we find a similar pattern to the main analysis, with M1 being the preferred model in a majority of
588 cases. Here we see on average 72% of clades with M1 as the best fit across seven machine learning
589 algorithms (Table S3; Fig S19).

590

591 *4.2.3 Phylogenetic metric calculation method*

592 Finally, to compare the impact of the method of phylogenetic metric calculations, we repeated the
593 model selection procedure using phylogenetic metrics (Spearman correlations with DR, MRD, ES,
594 ED, as well as Gamma, Colless's index and Sackin's index) calculated either on the MCC tree (Fig
595 S19c-d), or the mean values from across a sample of 50 trees from the posterior distribution (Fig
596 S19e-f). We found that clades had best fitting models in similar proportion using the MCC trees as in
597 the main analysis based on the posterior distribution (Table S3). M1 was the most common best fitting
598 model, and the proportion was marginally higher in the MCC-based analysis, compared to the
599 posterior analysis (Table S3), bringing the proportions in closer agreement to those based on time-
600 sliced clades which was also performed on the MCC tree (Fig S19a-b).

601

602 **Supplementary references**

603 Cohen J. 1960. A Coefficient of Agreement for Nominal Scales. *Educ. Psychol. Meas.* 20:37–46.

604 Constantinos T., Brody S. 2015. PhyloMeasures: a package for computing phylogenetic biodiversity
605 measures and their statistical moments. *Ecography (Cop.)*. 39:709–714.

606 Elith J., Leathwick J.R., Hastie T. 2008. A working guide to boosted regression trees. *J. Anim. Ecol.*
607 77:802–813.

608 Hagen O., Flück B., Fopp F., Cabral J.S., Hartig F., Pontarp M., Rangel T.F., Pellissier L. 2021a.

609 gen3sis: A general engine for eco-evolutionary simulations of the processes that shape Earth's
610 biodiversity. *PLoS Biol.* 19:e3001340.

611 Hagen O., Skeels A., Onstein R.E., Jetz W., Pellissier L. 2021b. Earth history events shaped the
612 evolution of uneven biodiversity across tropical moist forests. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*

613 Hurlbert A.H., Stegen J.C. 2014. When should species richness be energy limited , and how would we
614 know ? *Ecol. Lett.* 17:401–413.

615 Isaac N.J.B., Turvey S.T., Collen B., Waterman C., Baillie J.E.M. 2007. Mammals on the EDGE:
616 Conservation Priorities Based on Threat and Phylogeny. *PLoS One.* 2:e296.

617 Jetz W., Fine P.V.A. 2012. Global Gradients in Vertebrate Diversity Predicted by Historical Area-
618 Productivity Dynamics and Contemporary Environment. *PLoS Biol.* 10:e1001292–e1001292.

619 Jetz W., Thomas G.H., Joy J.B., Hartmann K., Mooers A.O. 2012. The global diversity of birds in
620 space and time. *Nature.* 491:444–448.

621 Jombart T., Balloux F., Dray S. 2010. adephylo: new tools for investigating the phylogenetic signal in
622 biological traits. *Bioinformatics.* 26:1907–1909.

623 Kembel S.W., Cowan P.D., Helmus M.R., Cornwell W.K., Morlon H., Ackerly D.D., Blomberg S.P.,
624 Webb C.O. 2010. Picante: R tools for integrating phylogenies and ecology. *Bioinformatics.*
625 26:1463–1464.

626 Levins R. 1966. The strategy of model building in population biology. *Am. Sci.* 54:421–431.

627 McHugh M.L. 2012. Interrater reliability: the kappa statistic. *Biochem. medica.* 22:276–282.

628 McPeck M.A. 2007. The macroevolutionary consequences of ecological differences among species.
629 *Palaeontology.* 50:111–129.

630 McPeck M.A. 2008. The ecological dynamics of clade diversification and community assembly. *Am.*
631 *Nat.* 172.

632 Mittelbach G.G., Schemske D.W. 2015. Ecological and evolutionary perspectives on community

633 assembly. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 30:241–247.

634 Olson D.M., Dinerstein E., Wikramanayake E.D., Burgess N.D., Powell G.V.N., Underwood E.C.,
635 D’Amico J.A., Itoua I., Strand H.E., Morrison J.C., Loucks C.J., Allnutt T.F., Ricketts T.H.,
636 Kura Y., Lamoreux J.F., Wettengel W.W., Hedao P., Kassem K.R. 2001. Terrestrial ecoregions
637 of the world: A new map of life on Earth. *Bioscience.* 51:933–938.

638 Pinheiro J., Bates D., DebRoy S., Sarkar D. 2020. *nlme: Linear and Nonlinear Mixed Effects Models.*
639 .

640 Prowse T.A.A., Bradshaw C.J.A., Delean S., Cassey P., Lacy R.C., Wells K., Aiello-Lammens M.E.,
641 Akçakaya H.R., Brook B.W. 2016. An efficient protocol for the global sensitivity analysis of
642 stochastic ecological models. *Ecosphere.* 7:e01238.

643 Redding D.W., Mooers A.Ø. 2006. Incorporating evolutionary measures into conservation
644 prioritization. *Conserv. Biol.* 20:1670–1678.

645 Scotese C.R., Song H., Mills B.J.W., van der Meer D.G. 2021. Phanerozoic paleotemperatures: The
646 earth’s changing climate during the last 540 million years. *Earth-Science Rev.* 215:103503.

647 Signorell A. 2021. *DescTools: Tools for descriptive statistics.* .

648 Viechtbauer W. 2010. Conducting meta-analyses in R with the metafor. *J. Stat. Softw.* 36:1–48.

649 Webb C.O. 2000. Exploring the phylogenetic structure of ecological communities: An example for
650 rain forest trees. *Am. Nat.* 156:145–155.

651 Webb C.O., Losos J.B., Agrawal A.A. 2006. Integrating phylogenies into community ecology.
652 *Ecology.* 87.

653